

POP

X City of
X Amsterdam
X

Image credits: Wikipedia

WHAT ARE POPULAR ANNUAL FINANCIAL REPORTS?

Popular Annual Financial Reports (PAFRs) are concise, user-friendly financial documents produced by government entities, typically at the local or municipal level, to communicate important financial information to the general public.

These reports are designed to make complex financial data more accessible and understandable to a wider audience, including citizens, taxpayers, and other stakeholders who may not have a background in finance or accounting.

Femke Hanselma,
Amsterdam's Mayor

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Mayor's Letter
2. General Data and Context
3. Rankings and Positioning
4. Public Administration Group
5. Consolidated Financial Statements
6. Description of Major Policies
7. Methodological Note
8. Dissemination Plan

Public Domain Pictures

MAYOR'S LETTER

“Dear members of the Council,

I have now been mayor for over five years and it is time to inform you if I wish to be considered for reappointment in 2024. Yes, I do, wholeheartedly. It would be an honour to serve our beautiful city for another term. [...] Together with the City Council, the municipal executive and all Amsterdammers, I want to continue working for a free, undivided, safe and proud city.

On being installed as mayor in July 2018, I described safeguarding freedom as my greatest responsibility. I mentioned three major tasks: fighting crime, paying more attention to Amsterdammers in neighbourhoods where prosperity is not a given, and supporting everyone who claims the right to be themselves, and thus sometimes to be different.

Back then, no one could have suspected how much the COVID-19 epidemic would restrict our freedom for nearly two years, nor how the attacks on Derk Wiersum and Peter R. de Vries would test our rule of law. In recent years, the number of demonstrations has increased significantly, we were the first city in the Netherlands to apologise for slavery and we welcomed large groups of refugees, including many fleeing the war in Ukraine.

The three major tasks I identified in 2018 are anchored at the heart of my mayoralty. Whether it is the fight against the drug economy, against increasing antisemitism and racism, against the ongoing violence against LGBTQ+ people and women. [...]

The over-tourism resulting in disruption in the inner city has led to a substantial change in policy that should take effect in the coming years. [...] For me, the essence of Amsterdam is the promise of the freedom to pursue your happiness and take your destiny into your own hands. Uncertainty over livelihoods, loneliness and a lack of safety mean too many Amsterdammers are prevented from doing so. I want to keep working on their behalf with as much determination as I have in recent years. [...]

In conclusion, the past few years have been dramatic, instructive, intense and sometimes tough, especially for those around me who have made sacrifices. However, when I take stock, I am grateful to all the people of Amsterdam whom I have had the privilege of meeting. Sometimes in great sorrow for the loss of a loved one, sometimes in celebration, sometimes deeply indignant and angry. Together, they are the soul of the city and it is a great privilege that I have been able to get so close to them.

I would also like to thank you deeply for our open, honest and close cooperation. I look forward to continuing it.

Warmest regards,
Femke Halsema”

GENERAL DATA AND CONTEXT

Inhabitants: 820.000
Inhabitants in greater Amsterdam: 1.498.000
Nationalities: 173
Bicycles: 600.000
Parks: 28
Markets: 21
Antique shops: 165
Diamond polishing factories: 24
Canals: 165
Bridges: 1.281
Houseboats: 2.500
Windmills: 6
Museums: 51
Art galleries: 141
Concerts and theatrical performances per year: 16.000
Theaters and concert halls: 55
Day-visitors per year: 15.854.000
Average income: 42000€/year

Amsterdam's population by age, of which:

- 308,000 immigrants (2022)
- 463,800 women VS 454,300 men
- 4.8% unemployed (2022)

ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT

FACTS:

- The Netherlands ranks 7th worldwide in the 2023 Global Innovation Index
- Amsterdam named most innovative small city in 2023
- The municipality of Amsterdam has the largest municipal budget in the Netherlands

- 1 University-Industry research collaboration:** A vast network of innovation districts offers collaborations to public and private entities to come together and involve citizens in shaping a better future through applied technology. There are 7 main universities in Amsterdam, which offer different courses for any field. Average tuition fee is 8000€.
- 2 Financial and business environment:** Very well developed startup ecosystem which attracts investors from all around the world, fueled by favorable entrepreneurship policies and tax regimes. Thanks to this favorable environment the AI and tech sector is flourishing.
- 3 Logistic trade:** Thanks to its history and its strategic position, the port of Amsterdam keeps being a strategic logistic hub for global trade. Thanks to the City Logistics Innovation Campus (CLIC) the port becomes everyday more efficient.
- 4 Creative Industry:** The city is a creative hub for creative industries, including design, fashion, advertising, and the arts. Numerous design studios, galleries, and cultural institutions are based in the city.
- 5 Sustainability:** One of the first cities to implement the “smart city” approach for a sustainable urban environment. There are also many pioneering eco friendly initiatives to boost biodiversity and shape a greener society from the ground up: for example, the widespread use of bicycles. In fact, Amsterdam aims to produce 0 emissions by 2030 and to implement a completely circular economy by 2050. Green finance is at the core of this development.
- 6 Culture:** Amsterdam’s 800 years of age have shaped a unique cultural heritage, which can be found in the countless museums, art shows, galleries, exhibitions, churches, canal houses, historical buildings, cinemas, theatres, museums, bars and so much more. In this nevralgic hub it’s impossible to be bored!

RANKINGS AND POSITIONING: OECD IN THE NETHERLANDS

LIFE SATISFACTION

- Dutch people on average gave it a 7.5 grade

SAFETY

- About 83% of people say that they feel safe walking alone at night
- The Netherland's homicide rate is 0.6

Life Satisfaction

8.7

Safety

8.9

Work-Life Balance

8.3

WORK LIFE BALANCE

- 0.3% of employees work very long hours in paid work
- **full-time workers devote 64% of their day on average, or 15.4 hours, to personal care** (eating, sleeping, etc.) **and leisure** (socialising with friends and family, hobbies, games, computer...)

RANKINGS AND POSITIONING

Housing

7.5

Income

4.1

Jobs

9.1

Community

8.0

oecdbetterlifeindex.org

HOUSING

- 20% of Dutch gross adjusted disposable income goes on keeping a roof over their heads
- The average Dutch home contains 2 rooms per person

INCOME

- In the Netherlands, the average household net adjusted disposable income per capita is USD 34 984 a year
- Average household net wealth is estimated at USD 248 599

JOBS

- About 78% of the working-age population aged 15 to 64 has a paid job
- Labour force that has been unemployed for a year or longer is currently at about 0.9%; workers face an expected 2.5% loss of earnings if they become unemployed
- Dutch people earn USD 58 828 per year on average
- Employment rate: 77.79%
- Job security: 2.55%

COMMUNITY

- 94% of people believe that they know someone they could rely on in a time of need

RANKINGS AND POSITIONING

Education

7.7

Environment

7.6

Civic engagement

7.4

Health

8.2

oecdbetterlifeindex.org

HEALTH

- Life expectancy in the Netherlands is at 82 years
- 75% of people in the Netherlands reported to be in good health

CIVIC ENGAGEMENT

- 94% of people believe that they know someone whose life expectancy in the Netherlands is at 82 years
- 75% of people in the Netherlands reported to be in good health
- They could rely on in a time of need

EDUCATION

- People in the Netherlands can expect to go through nearly 18.8 years of education between the ages of 5 and 39
- 81% of adults aged 25-64 have completed upper secondary education
- The average student in the Netherlands scored 502 in reading literacy, maths and sciences, above the OECD average of 488.

ENVIRONMENT

- PM2.5 levels are 12.2 micrograms per cubic meter, lower than the OECD average
- 91% of people say they are satisfied with water quality

GOVERNING BODIES OF AMSTERDAM

The **city council**, the **College of Mayors and Alderpersons**, the **district committees** and the **administrative committee for Weesp** together form the Amsterdam city government. The city council is the highest governing body and consists of elected representatives of the people of Amsterdam.

The **city council** has 45 members, of which the **mayor** is the chairperson. The council establishes the general policies of the City of Amsterdam and monitors the **College of Mayor and Alderpersons**, which is implementing that policy. A term of office on the council lasts 4 years, and the current term is from 2022 to 2026.

- The **College of Mayor and Alderpersons** proposes decisions to the council, which decides for approval or rejection. The council can respond in various ways or submit their own topics.
- The majority of topics that are presented to the city council are prepared beforehand by a **city council committee**. The city council committee is composed by experts from the political parties.

CITY COUNCIL COMMITTEES

- *General Affairs*
- *Sustainability and Circular Economy*
- *Finance, Art and Diversity*
- *Mobility, Public Space and Water*
- *Education, Health and Poverty prevention*
- *Spatial Planning*
- *Social Affairs, Economy and Democratization*
- *City Development*
- *Housing construction and public housing*

POLITICAL PARTIES AND THEIR REPRESENTATIVES

PvdA: 9
GroenLinks: 8
D66: 7
VVD: 5
BIJ1: 3
Partij voor de Dieren: 3
SP: 2
Volt: 2
DENK: 2
JA21: 2
CDA: 1
Forum voor Democratie: 1

=> 23 men and 21 women

COLLEGE OF MAYOR AND ALDERPERSONS

COLLEGE OF MAYOR AND ALDERPERSONS

The College of Mayor and Alderperson' functions are:

1. **Daily operations**
2. **Policy implementation**
3. **Choice of the alderpersons:**
there are seven alderpersons, each with their own portfolio of topics

The meetings of the College of Mayor and Alderpersons are not open to the public.

MAYOR

The mayor is the **chairperson** of both the College of Mayor and Alderpersons and the city council. The national government appoints the mayor.

The Mayor is responsible for:

- **General Affairs**
- **Public Order and Safety**
- **Integrated Safety Management**
- **Legal Affairs**
- **Communications**
- **Council Affairs**
- **Enforcement and Inspection.**

www.amsterdam.nl/en/governance/the-college-of-mayor-and-alderpersons/

> Mayor Femke Halsema

> Marjolein Moorman

> Rutger Groot Wassink

> Reinier van Dantzig

> Sofyan Mbarki

> Zita Pels

> Melanie van der Horst

> Hester van Buren

> Touria Meliani

> Alexander Scholtes

> Peter Teesink

DISTRICTS AND NEIGHBOURHOODS

Amsterdam has **7 city districts** and the **administrative committee for Weesp**:
Centre, Nieuw-West, Noord, Oost, West, Zuid, Zuidoost.

Each city district is managed by a **district committee** with **3 managing directors** appointed by the College of Mayor and Alderpersons. The managing directors are supported by an **advisory committee**, which number of components depends on number of inhabitants of the district.

The committee is the **link** between the **district and City Hall**. They deal with important topics in the district, such as the design of streets and squares, public greenery and parks, household waste collection, and social work in the neighbourhood: the committees operate as the **City's eyes and ears**.

Weesp is now part of the municipality of Amsterdam, having become part of a new 'urban area' that also includes the town of **Driemond**.

Weesp has its own administrative committee, area team and City Office where residents and businesses can go with questions and comments.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The municipal organisation consists of 5 clusters, the services support teams, and 8 district organisations, responsible for executive tasks.

Gemeente Amsterdam

CLUSTERS

The clusters are:

1. Economic Services
2. Social Services
3. Community Services
4. Public Space Management
5. Operational Services (provides support to civil servants and the municipal organisation)

THE CLUSTERS

ECONOMIC SERVICES DEPARTMENTS

- Economic Affairs
- City Development
- Mobility and Public Space
- Planning and Sustainability
- Housing
- Estates
- Parking
- Materials and Equipment
- Zuidas district
- Project Management
- Project Engineering
- Special projects

AREA BASED APPROACH AND PUBLIC SPACE MANAGEMENT

- Waste and Recycling
- Public Works
- Local Taxes
- Resident and Business Services
- Public Space Surveillance and Enforcement
- 7 City Districts and Urban Area of Weesp

SOCIAL SERVICES DEPARTMENTS

- Work, Community Participation and Income
- GGD Amsterdam - Public Health Service of Amsterdam
- Sports and Recreation
- Education, Youth and Welfare Services
- Subsidies, Procurement and Legal Bureau Social Services
- Social Services Support Team (support department)

OPERATIONAL SERVICES

- Communications Department
- Facilities
- Finance and Procurement
- Professional Support
- Legal Bureau
- Human Resources Department
- VGA Insurance

COMMUNITY SERVICES DEPARTMENTS

- Digitalisation and Innovation
- Digital Strategy and Information
- Data
- Digital Facilities
- City Archives

CONSOLIDATED FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

INCOME

TOT: €3.3839,6 millions

Income within the municipality

- LOCAL CHARGES: €1.149,3
- OTHER SOURCE OF INCOME: €2.690,3

INCOME

TOT: **€3.761.7 millions**

Income from the state

TOT INCOME: €7.601,3

millions

EXPENDITURE

Amsterdam has the largest municipal budget of The Netherlands. The budget gives us an overview of the income and expenditure of the municipality of this city.

TOT EXPENDITURE: €7.404,8

millions

FINANCIAL AUTONOMY - To what extent is the municipality of Amsterdam financially dependent on others government bodies (e.g. central government, EU, province)?

A high positive percentage implies a high degree of independence
= Proceeds from fees, charges and taxes/revenue generated from operations business activities

2021: 25% - **2022: 27%**

DEBT

- **Cost of Debt** - This figure shows the relationship between the external interest costs and the revenue generated from operational business activities. A low percentage is positive, because this indicates that interest costs are low in relation to operating income business activities

= External interest costs/income from operating activities business activities and the expenses from operational business activities

2021: 1% - **2022: 1%**

- **Debt Repayment Capacity** - How large is the long-term debt at the end of the financial year in relation to the revenue from operational business activities? The ratio is comparable to the Stability and Growth Pact, Maastricht Treaty and the Gross Domestic Product.

= Long-term debt at the end of the financial year/revenue generated from business activities

2021: 128% - **2022: 123%**

- **Debt Repayment Length** - How many years will it take to pay off the current debt? The lower the number of years, the better.

= The long-term debts at the end of the financial year/repayments of the private loans.

2021: 21 - **2022: 19**

- **Debt Paydown Capacity** - How long will it take to pay off the current debt as the gross realized result is used?

The lower the number of years, the better.

= The long-term debts at the end of the financial year/endgross realized result.

2021: 22 - **2022: 16**

BALANCE

- **Overall Financial Flows Balance** - How large is the overall surplus/deficit in the financial transaction flows?

A positive value implies that a positive return is achieved in the past investments made in financial fixed assets. For example, dividend income participation X.

= The sum of the (dis)investments in the financial fixed assets/the revenue generated from the operational business activities

- **Net Lending or Borrowing Capacity** -

What is the surplus/deficit in the operational and financial business activities?

A positive value implies that a return is being made on past work investments.

=The net financing requirement / generated revenue from operational business activities

- **Operating Balance** - Is there a balance between the revenue from the operational business activities = The generated revenue from the operational and the expenses from operational business activities (including loan repayments)?

A percentage higher than 100% means that new investments can be made in assets financed without taking out new loans. A percentage lower than 100% may indicate on an imbalance.

= The revenue generated from the operational business activities/ (the sum of the realized expenses from operational business activities +/- de repayments of the private loans)

DESCRIPTION OF MAJOR POLICIES

TRANSPARENCY IS KEY

The City of Amsterdam regularly publishes Planning & Control (P&C) documents that provide insight into the city's revenue and expenditures

☆ 2014 - Amsterdam's College of Mayor and Alderpersons makes putting the city's finances in order a top priority. This was the start of a series of improvements

☆ 2016 - The city of Amsterdam launched a programme known as "**Finance In Order**". Twice per year, the College of Mayor and Alderpersons reports to the City Council on ongoing measures to regulate city finances and on any improvements that are still necessary.

Until the end of 2018, the focus will remain on bringing order to Amsterdam's finances and providing a solid financial foundation, particularly through improvements in the following areas:

- Organisational structure, including duties, authority, and responsibilities
- Administrative organisation and internal control (AO/IC) of critical financial processes
- Financial administration
- Financial management information
- Encouraging desired behaviour and a learning organisation.

2014-2018 ACCOMPLISHMENTS

1. CENTRALISED ADMINISTRATION

Amsterdam went from having 44 separate administrative departments for a variety of services and city districts, each with its own procedures and regulations, to a single, unified administration for the entire city with clear regulations, processes, and responsibilities.

This transition has greatly improved transparency and has brought the city's payment processes into line with Dutch regulations

2. CLEAR BUDGET AND FINANCIAL REGULATIONS

Budgetary rules have been established to define members' responsibilities in certain situations, such as in the event of overspending.

The City of Amsterdam's financial regulations (agreements between the College of Mayor and Alderpersons and the City Council) have also been updated.

EX. applications for new investments may now only be submitted once per year.

The budget has been *streamlined* and made *more transparent*.

Better balance sheet projections have been made, improving insight into future revenue and expenditures.

Investment forecasts have been updated, providing a better picture of upcoming expenditures.

Excess reserves have been eliminated, freeing up more money to invest in the city.

Unnecessary credits have been eliminated

3. SUBSIDIES

A public register of all Amsterdam subsidies is available online so that everyone can see how they are allocated.

4. INVESTMENTS

The City of Amsterdam has invested in anti-fraud measures, in the Amsterdam Tax Service, and in ACAM Accountancy.

There have also been investments in financial control, organisation and administration

5. TAXES

A number of taxes have been eliminated, including dog-licence fees and advertising tax, thereby reducing the burden on Amsterdammers and small businesses.

Sewerage charge (*rioolheffing*) is now calculated based on the actual amount of water used. As a result, rates have fallen by 15% for everyone with a sewer connection, including all homeowners. High-volume users such as cafes and restaurants, industrial establishments, and car wash facilities now pay more, depending on their water consumption.

KEY POLICIES THEMES

TOURISM

**TRAFFIC AND
TRANSPORTATION**

GREEN SPACE

**SUSTAINABILITY
AND ENERGY**

TOURISM

set maximum number of visitors to prevent nuisances

Some examples:

- reduce bachelor parties
- restrict river cruises
- distribute tourism evenly
- convert hotels into homes or offices
- introduce earlier closing times for bars and clubs in certain parts of the city centre
- introduce a ban on smoking cannabis on the street in certain parts of the city centre

20 MILLION
VISITORS PER YEAR

Amsterdam is known internationally as a free and open city.

But recently this freedom has been exploited for commercial purposes., selling Amsterdam as a place where everything is possible and allowed.

Therefore the city encourages creative and sustainable businesses which offer products or activities that are fun for tourists and make a positive contribution to the city and the lives of the people of Amsterdam.

TRAFFIC AND TRANSPORT

Research has shown that the majority (40-60%) of traffic in the city centre is *'through traffic'*.

Amsterdam's city government is working on this while keeping the area accessible for residents, visitors, and suppliers.

Measures designed to improve traffic flow, relocate heavy traffic to the outskirts of the city and reduce through traffic will have the added benefit of improving air quality.

- By 2030, Amsterdam's population density will have increased from 5,100 residents per square kilometre to 5,700.

While it is important that the city continues to expand, it is also important that Amsterdam remains accessible to everyone even though there's not enough room to accommodate bicycles, pedestrians, public transport and cars side by side everywhere in the city.

Cars are very discouraged and most of the people will not be needing to own them

A wide range of measures were introduced in the Mobility Plan for Amsterdam in 2030

Key goals include:

- Creating more space in the city centre
 - Restricting car traffic and introducing 30 km/h zones.
 - Introducing new cycle bridges and ferry services
 - Building more underground parking
- Improving traffic flow on important routes

TRAFFIC SAFETY

Methods for improving safety include giving pedestrians and cyclists more room and reducing speed limits for cars.

GREEN SPACE

The policy document Comprehensive Vision Amsterdam 2050 sets out the City Council's strategy for green space. The Main Green Space Infrastructure plan protects and enhances important green spaces in the city.

Green vision 2020-2050

The Green Infrastructure Vision paints a picture of Amsterdam as a green city and sets out how we will work towards achieving that vision between now and 2050.

Measures to be taken include:

- Green routes: A 10-minute walk from your front door to a park, a 15-minute bike ride to a nature reserve.
- A 'green by default' principle
- Public and accessible green spaces
- Landscape parks
- New forest and parks

SUSTAINABILITY AND ENERGY

It is no secret that the effect of the climate change are more and more frequent and intense, the city of Amsterdam has taken things into action

OUR CITY OF TOMORROW - action plan

The city pays attention especially to:

- phasing out natural gas
- installing solar panels on the city's roofs
- re using materials

The City's climate goals

- **2030**

All traffic within the A10 ring road is emission free

Operations of the municipal organisation are entirely sustainable

80% of the energy used by households comes from solar and wind energy

Use of raw materials is reduced by 50%

CO2 emissions are reduced by 60% compared to 1990

- **2040**

Natural gas is completely phased out

All suitable roofs are being utilised for generating solar energy

- **2050**

The city is fully prepared for climate change (it is 'climate adaptive')

The city is fully climate neutral, with no CO2 emissions

Circular economy principles are fully implemented

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

Amsterdam, the capital of the Netherlands, is a multifaceted city of historical, cultural, and economic significance. Researching Amsterdam involves a methodological approach tailored to its complexity:

Data Sources: Comprehensive data collection is essential, including official statistics from the Central Bureau of Statistics, historical documents from the Amsterdam City Archives, surveys, geospatial data, qualitative interviews, and online data.

Research Methodologies: Researchers employ diverse methodologies, depending on their discipline: historical research relies on archival records and oral history; urban studies employ spatial analysis and fieldwork; sociologists use surveys and content analysis; economists apply quantitative methods; geographers leverage GIS and remote sensing. Multidisciplinary approaches are often needed for a holistic view.

Ethical Considerations: Adherence to ethical principles is crucial, including informed consent, privacy protection, cultural sensitivity, data protection laws, and harm minimization.

Data Analysis: Researchers use appropriate statistical tools and contextualize findings within Amsterdam's historical and cultural context.

In conclusion, studying Amsterdam offers a diverse array of research opportunities across multiple disciplines. Researchers must carefully select data sources, methodologies, and uphold ethical standards to gain valuable insights into the city's complex and ever-evolving nature. Amsterdam's unique historical, cultural, and urban development characteristics make it a compelling subject for academic investigation and policy analysis.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

Our research on Amsterdam aims to provide valuable insights into the city's diverse dynamics and multifaceted aspects. The dissemination plan outlines a strategy for sharing our findings effectively.

- 1. Academic Publications:** preparing scholarly articles for publication in reputable journals across relevant disciplines such as urban studies, geography, sociology, and economics. These articles will undergo peer review to ensure academic rigor.
- 2. Reports and Policy Briefs:** To engage policymakers and stakeholders, we will create concise reports and policy briefs summarizing our research findings and their implications for urban development, cultural preservation, and economic growth in Amsterdam.
- 3. Public Presentations:** organize public presentations and seminars within Amsterdam to foster community engagement. These events will be open to the public, and we will encourage discussions and questions from attendees.
- 4. Online Presence:** Creating a dedicated website or blog to share our research findings, infographics, and interactive maps can help reach a broader online audience, including residents and tourists interested in Amsterdam.
- 5. Media Outreach:** Collaborating with local and international media outlets for interviews, op-eds, and feature articles can increase the visibility of our research and raise awareness about Amsterdam's unique characteristics.
- 6. Social Media:** Leveraging social media platforms to share key findings, engage with a wider audience, and encourage discussions and feedback on our research.
- 7. Collaboration:** seek opportunities to collaborate with local institutions, universities, and city agencies to ensure that our research contributes to ongoing initiatives and policy development in Amsterdam.

This comprehensive dissemination plan ensures that our research on Amsterdam reaches academic, policy, and public audiences, allowing us to make a meaningful contribution to the understanding and development of this vibrant and historic city.

“This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the SAA, University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra.”